

ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY IN TOURIST ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: In the article, the issues of the development of entrepreneurial activity in the tourist enterprises of our country are studied on the basis of theoretical research. At the same time, the main branches of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism, the directions of the impact of the entrepreneurial structure on economic efficiency in tourism activities, as well as the risks that may arise in tourist enterprises working in the B2B system and ways to minimize it are studied.

Keywords: tourism, entrepreneurship, tourism entrepreneurship, SWOT analysis, model, tourism networks.

The formation of a market economy in Uzbekistan coincided with a period of sharp changes in the field of tourism in world markets. In the world, the tourism sector has become one of the most significant sectors of the economy. The tourism industry employs about a million workers and servants, providing opportunities for the growth of professional skills. It should be noted that the employment situation in this area is growing twice as fast as in other areas. The development of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism is influenced by socio-economic, technical and technological factors.

The complexity and uncertainty of medium and long-term planning in the development of entrepreneurship in the activities of tourism enterprises determines the importance of the time factor, which is characterized by a high variability of the external environment. Therefore, the functioning of entrepreneurship in the direction of tourism should be considered as a continuous process, changing planning, implementation and control of plans. It is also referred to as the process of determining the results, managing the situation and controlling and regulating the results. In our opinion, the way out of the situation that has arisen is to develop a strategy for the development of entrepreneurial activity at the state level in tourist enterprises, based on the approaches proposed above.

The external macroenvironment of entrepreneurship is not considered a direct object of entrepreneurship in the activities of the organization, and its transformation must be under the direct control of the state. From a scientific point of view, the greatest practical interest in the study of entrepreneurial activity comes directly from the external business microenvironment and the internal business environment, which is the object of entrepreneurial influences. For the effective development of entrepreneurial activity, it is necessary to monitor the state of the main factors of the macro and microenvironment, which directly or indirectly affect the final result of the organization of tourism activities¹.

¹ Гогоберидзе Г.Г., Аверкиев А.С. Экономика прибрежной зоны.// Российский государственный гидрометеорологический университет. – Санкт-Петербург, 2003 г. -155 с.

This requires the implementation of a SWOT analysis showing the strengths and weaknesses, risks and opportunities of the activities in the area where tourism activities are being established. The SWOT analysis to be carried out allows the formation of the following main development strategic directions of Tourism and excursion activities in the natural-economic region or region:

- to ensure the transparency of the policy of regulatory structures of the state in the field of tourism activities and to achieve the results of these activities, cooperation is carried out by territorial governing bodies, including on the lease and long-term use of natural facilities;
- introduction of mechanisms for the joint development of tourism activities in the natural-economic region with all interested parties in order to take advantage of new resources and opportunities;
- implementation of an effective system for regulating the flow of tourists in the area where tourism activities are being developed;
- the use of marketing elements in territorial and project planning of regulatory facilities and elements in the zone of Tourism and tourist-excursion services.

At the same time, the main problem in the process of forming a strategy for the development of entrepreneurial activity in the organization of tourism activities is the variety of natural complexes of ecosystems and their corresponding development methods, the organization of visitors from different groups, the abundance of influence of local residents and enterprises. In order to effectively solve the tasks of conservation and tourism in such conditions, it is necessary to apply the functional zoning or division of the territory to departments of different priority purposes and in different modes of protection and use.

The peculiarities of the tourism sector also determine the joint organization and development of the tourist complex by the state and business sector. On the basis of the "joint participation" of interested parties in countries with a developed economy, the mechanism of organization and development of a tourist complex has been formed.

In the scientific literature, there are three types of models of state participation in the regulation of Tourism.

The first model is unique to the United States, the main features of which are the absence of a central state body regulating tourism and the existence of the principles of "self-regulation". This model is typical of countries where tourism is not the main source of income in the national economy or where the subjects of the tourist market can solve their problems without state intervention. The main reasons for the transition to such a model of organization and development are as follows:

- lack of opportunities to finance the industry from the federal budget;
- the presence of a formed tourist image of the state and, as a result, the absence of the need for additional advertising;
- the presence of economically strong and independent tourism enterprises that can solve issues in the interests of the entire national market.

The second model is typical for countries such as Egypt, Turkey, Tunisia, where tourism is one of the main sources of income. The main features of the operation of this model are the presence of a central governing body for all enterprises and, as a result, the state financial support of the entire tourist and Recreational Complex. This model is typical for countries where it is necessary to create certain conditions for the development of the tourism industry. The main condition is significant financial investments in the form of investments in the

tourism industry, in particular in advertising and marketing activities, the tourism industry and infrastructure

The third model is typical for European countries. A distinctive feature of this model is the coordination by the Ministry of tourism industry of general issues (regulatory legal, coordination of regional bodies, International Cooperation) and regulation of marketing activities aimed at placing national tourism products in the International and domestic tourism market. In countries where such a model applies, issues related to the development of tourism activities are solved by a multidisciplinary state system at the level of the relevant network unit. This model is typical of countries such as Germany, France, Spain, Great Britain and other countries of the European Union, Russia.

Analysis of the development and state of regulation of tourism structures formed in our country today shows that a separate form of the above-mentioned models is not used, the development system is in the form of a combination of all three models.

Within the framework of the implementation of the study, the methods of organizing the strategic development of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism are summarized and systematized by assessing the level of diversification in the accumulation of resources. Diversification is manifested in the need to use various material and intangible resources, production technologies, professional skills and skills to provide each specific service. Therefore, the tourism sector demonstrates a broader and more diverse organizational structure than other sectors of the service sector².

The tourism sector is a real economy sector that provides multidisciplinary services to consumers in the process of using tourism resources. In turn, in the structure of entrepreneurship in the field of tourism, an independent business entity engaged in the formation, development and sale of services to tourists is understood, as well as other additional types of economic activities established by the Charter of the enterprise and not prohibited by the legislation of the country (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The main branches of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism³

The nature of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism is manifested as a unity of

² Юй И. Управление развитием предпринимательских структур в сфере гостеприимства (на примере КНР). Автореферат на соискание учёной степени кандидата экономических наук. –М.: МЭСИ, 2015. – 27 с.

³ Developed by the author.

interconnected functions. The development of the tourism sector at the state level in any country is carried out using regulatory legal acts on the basis of increasing national income from entrepreneurial activity of business entities in this area, maintaining tourist resources and protecting consumer rights. The branch level of regulation of entrepreneurial activity consists in the development of the industry by them in combination with foreign tourist organizations at the expense of the production of high-quality tourist products and services, replenishment of the domestic market. The level of domestic production is determined by the organizational and legal form of Organization of the tourism industry, its size, types of services, strategic purpose of development, the need to increase competitiveness, maintain constant groups of consumers and win new ones.

In the process of research, the influence of organizational and economic methods for the development of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism on the development of the resource potential of the industry is determined. Entrepreneurial structures affect costs and profitability through effective economic systems, as a result, the overall efficiency of activities (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Impact of the structure of entrepreneurship on economic efficiency in tourism activities⁴

The assessment of economic efficiency in entrepreneurial structures begins with an analysis of the compatibility of the systems being used. Effective organizational structure, on the one hand, can improve the management process of decision making, planning, leadership, motivation and control to achieve high efficiency. On the other hand, it can affect the promotion and restriction of the number of employees, reduce the costs of internal management of the organization.

Exogenous factors can include economic, political, stichian factors as well as seasonal factors. Endogenous factors include a lack of financial, material and labor resources, which reduces the competitive advantages of a certain entrepreneurial structure over others in satisfying the needs and desires of users of tourism services.

Among the main entrepreneurial risks faced by enterprises of the tourism industry are the following risks:

- choosing a tourist route, the total costs for the production of a tourist product exceed

⁴ Юй, И. Меры государственного регулирования и поддержки предпринимательства в сфере туризма Китая [Текст] / И. Юй // Модель менеджмента для экономики, основанной на знаниях. Материалы конференции. – М.: МЭСИ, 2014. – С. 310-313

the sales prices specified in the contract;

Figure 2. Possible risks in tourist enterprises working in the B2B system ⁵

- the ability to organize hospitality, evaluate and pay for the proposed tourist product of various concepts and their needs.

For tourist enterprises of type B2B, the result of the activity that determines the effectiveness of their activities is the provision of tourist products and services. They should have quality characteristics that correspond to the needs of the activity of a tourist enterprise, which is the organizational center of the process. In this type of entrepreneurial communication, risks may arise in the relationship between tourist enterprises and turagentans, tourist enterprises and hotels, tourist enterprises and transport companies.

Based on a systematic analysis of the boundaries of the development of entrepreneurial structures of tourist enterprises in the field of Tourism and the identification of risks that limit entrepreneurial income and reduce efficiency, it can be concluded that the main factors

⁵ Developed on the basis of author's research.

for setting these boundaries are the structure, quality and scope of production, financial and organizational processes.

Thus, in the process of carrying out activities in tourist enterprises, there are various levels of economic efficiency, which, in turn, are directly and indirectly related to the establishment of the boundaries of the development of entrepreneurial structures of tourist enterprises. In many ways, these limits depend on the state of the internal environment of the entrepreneurial structure, the place of the tourist enterprises in the system, the direction and quality of the organizational, technical, management, personnel service, as well as the possibilities of forming a single structure of tourist enterprises in the direction of the common goal is a tourist and production environment.

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